

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF MANAGEMENT OF THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM ON THE BASIS OF CORPORATE CULTURE

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Abstract: This article presents the diagnosis of corporate culture formation. Such diagnoses reveal the level of knowledge of students about the nature and meaningful aspects of personal culture and attitudes. The concept of a person's corporate culture, its structure, criteria and indicators are determined.

Key words: Coaching and teaching service, Collaboration and community, Counseling students, Convenient and innovative teaching methods, Development of learning processes for all participants, Achievement of goals.

The main part: The economic problems of our country are worsening and the demands for training high-level specialists are increasing day by day. In connection with the changes taking place in society, problems arise in the organization of the content of higher education of high-level specialists. The main role in solving this problem should be given to a system specially created for the formation of corporate culture of students in a higher education institution.

If we look at history, in the middle of the 20th century, experts came to the conclusion that the success of all prosperous organizations that know their business well and have a clear purpose, principles, includes the idea of corporate culture. Due to the dynamic nature of the state of corporate culture, there was a need to develop methods of monitoring and subsequent adaptation of the corporate culture of organizations. In modern conditions, corporate culture is studied through the prism of enterprise efficiency, increasing the competitiveness of enterprises, labor efficiency of employees of commercial structures, psychological environment in the team, and problems of employee loyalty to the organization. In the higher education institution, it is customary to describe the concepts of "Corporate culture" using the terms "corporation" and "culture".

The purpose of the article is to diagnose the formation of corporate culture among students and to reveal the specific formation of the above-mentioned phenomenon in the educational environment of any university.

The purpose of the research is to reveal the meaningful aspects of the corporate culture of students, to study the formation of general indicators for their corporate culture, and to justify the technology of forming the corporate culture of students in the educational environment of their own university.

Pedagogical conditions for managing the higher education system based on corporate culture are as follows:

- + Mentoring and teacher service: Teachers and mentors must provide high quality service to students. It is necessary for them to have regular contact with students, to understand them well and to help them achieve their goals.
- + Cooperation and community: Teachers and coaches must ensure that students cooperate, develop a community spirit, and ensure participation in all educational processes.
- + Counseling students: Teachers and coaches should be effective in counseling students, help them solve their problems, identify their goals and not help them.
- + Convenient and innovative teaching methods: Teachers and trainers should use new and innovative teaching methods, motivate students and organize interesting lessons for them.
- + Development of learning processes for all participants: Teachers and coaches should develop learning processes for all participants, introducing the individual needs and goals of each student.
- + Realization of goals: Teachers and coaches should understand the goals of students, guide them in a way to achieve them, and create favorable conditions for them.

Based on these conditions, it is possible to develop the pedagogical skills of managing the higher education system based on corporate culture.

In relation to the organization, the term "corporation" is used when we want to emphasize that the organization is considered as a whole, therefore, the values of the corporate culture of the organization should be accepted by all employees and they are intended to work to achieve greater harmony of the team. should be.

The characteristics of the corporation are felt in the following characteristics of the higher education institution:

- ✓ institutional and organizational stability (a higher education institution independently develops performance standards and its own structure);
- ✓ specific narrow field of activity, uniqueness of the product (science and higher education);

- ✓ acceptance of the surrounding space as a potential consumer of the product/a source of resources necessary for the corporation;
- ✓ participation in relations between "producer" and "consumer";
- ✓ involvement in competitive relations with manufacturers;
- ✓ self-identification as a whole and resistance to the competitive environment (existence of "corporate spirit");
- ✓ ownership of personnel and information resources that form the basis of corporate capital;
- ✓ local and network nature of higher education institution activity;
- ✓ common interests about relatives. The socio-economic status of most employees, which depends on the competitive environment and customer base that is forming around the higher education institution;
- ✓ Hierarchical social organization of many employees with possible "shifting of goals" - difference in the interests of managers and ordinary employees;

Summary:

The following pedagogical methods can be used to achieve the goals:

1. Individual approach: Teachers should understand the individual goals of students and approach them individually. In doing so, teachers need to identify students' interests and goals, understand their strengths and weaknesses, and not help them personally.
2. Practical activities: Teachers should organize practical activities to guide the students towards the objectives. This method is effective for putting students' theoretical knowledge to practical test, learning information through physical activities and developing students' skills.
3. Interactive lessons: Teachers should implement the objectives by providing interactive lessons to the students. This method provides opportunities for students to actively participate in the lesson, participate in questions and advice, express their opinions and communicate with other students.
4. Portfolio Creation: Teachers can implement the objectives by encouraging students to create personal portfolios. A portfolio shows students' achievements, work and developed skills and motivates them to achieve their goals.
5. Lessons related to the objectives: Teachers should organize lessons related to the objectives to realize the objectives. In these lessons, students will find opportunities

to complete goal-oriented tasks, solve puzzles, and evaluate their achievement of goals.

These pedagogic methods are effective for the implementation of goals in the learning process and increase the motivation of students.

References:

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasining 2020 yil 23 sentyabrdagi «Ta’lim to‘g‘risida»gi Qonuni.
2. Belova L.I. Rossiya oliy ta’lim muassasasining korporativ madaniyati ijtimoiymadaniy tahlil ob’ekti sifatida: Janubiy Ural davlat ta’lim muassasasi misolida: Chelyabinsk, 2009 yil.
3. Tyunnikov Yu, Maznichenko M. Korporativ madaniyat ta’lim muassasasining raqobatbardoshligi omili sifatida//Rossiyada oliy ta’lim. 2005 yil. № 10. 69-77-betlar.
4. Gonoshilina I.G. Ta’lim muassasasining kuchli korporativ madaniyati: o‘lchov parametrlari // Madaniyatshunoslik masalalari. 2009.
5. Osipov A.M. Ta’lim sotsiologiyasi: Nazariy insholar. R/D: Feniks, 2003.
6. Kapitonov E.A., Kapitonov A.E. Korporativ madaniyat. 2001 yil.
7. Gnezdilova N.K. Oliy ta’lim pedagogining korporativ madaniyati va uning ta’lim muassasasiga sodiqligi// Psixologiya. 2013 yil.